

Development of Real-Time Density Matrix Embedding Theory for the Application to Non-Equilibrium Spin Phenomena

Abstract—The cost of quantum-based computational chemistry methods scales exponentially with increasing system size, limiting the systems that can be studied using these methods. One affected area is chiral induced spin selectivity (CISS), a phenomenon in which a molecule’s chirality influences the spin of electrons passing through the molecule. To offer a solution to the problem of dimensionality and to study CISS, we are developing the real-time extension of the wavefunction-based projected density matrix embedding theory (RT-pDMET). Previous work has shown that RT-pDMET is able to accurately capture electron dynamics in model systems and converges to an exact solution. Current work focuses on developing a spin non-collinear RT-pDMET to correctly capture spin phenomena, in which an electron can adopt states beyond just spin-up or spin-down, as well as implementing MPI to take advantage of embarrassingly parallel parts of the algorithm. This method will then be applied to investigate the CISS effect but has wide-reaching applications in the study of spin dynamics.

I. INTRODUCTION

Advances in fields in which non-equilibrium electron dynamics underlie physical phenomena of interest, such as in ultrafast spectroscopy, necessitate the development of new theoretical methods that solve the time-dependent Schrödinger equation. [1] Highly accurate wavefunction-based methods have been developed, but these methods are only applicable to very small systems due to their high computational cost. For example, multi-configurational time-dependent Hartree (MCTDH) is a highly accurate method but scales exponentially with the number of degrees of freedom. [1] Other methods, such as real time density functional theory (RT-DFT) with much lower scaling can be applied to larger systems, but sacrifice accuracy for computational expense. [2] Additionally, some applications of electron dynamics also require a description of spin in which the spin state may not be fully spin up or spin down in order to be characterized correctly. This approach is referred to as either a generalized or non-collinear spin formalism, and further increases the computational expense. As a result, a methodology that can capture spin dynamics in systems larger than a few atoms while retaining accuracy is needed.

An example of these types of systems are chiral molecules, molecules that are nonsuperimposable on their mirror image. These molecules exhibit a phenomenon known as the chiral induced spin selectivity (CISS) effect in which the molecule’s chirality polarizes the spin of a current passing through the molecule to favor one spin state over another, as shown in Fig. 1. [3]–[7] The CISS effect have grown in interest in

Fig. 1. Diagram of a system exhibiting CISS behavior. Electrons passing through a chiral molecule between two electrodes begin in a mixture of up and down spins (blue and red), and end in a mostly uniform spin configuration (blue).

multiple fields due to their possible applications in spintronics, electronic devices in which spin is used to store or manipulate information, leading to greater efficiency and energy savings. [4], [6] Furthermore, the CISS effect is gaining interest in multiple areas of chemistry, such as a possible answer to the origins of homochirality in evolutionary biochemistry. [4] While much experimental work has focused on improving the magnitude of spin polarization and determining under what conditions the CISS effect appears, the mechanisms underlying CISS are still largely unknown. A deeper understanding of the mechanisms behind the CISS effect would allow for rapid innovation in spintronics, as well as contribute to discussions beginning in fields such as biochemistry. Previous theoretical work has shed some light on the current understanding of the CISS effect, but new methodologies capable of capturing the transient electron dynamics through a chiral molecule are needed to fully develop our understanding of this phenomenon. [5]

Reformulating the description of a system into an embedding framework is a way to tackle the ‘curse of dimensionality’ associated with quantum-based methodologies. In an embedding approach, a subsystem of interest is treated at a high level of theory and everything else in the system is reduced to the environment, or bath, and treated at a lower level of theory. In order to characterize spin phenomena while balancing computational cost and accuracy, we are developing real-time projected density matrix embedding theory (RT-pDMET) in the spin generalized formalism. In RT-pDMET, the most computationally expensive step is based on the methods used to treat the subsystems and can be set by the user. While both timing and memory requirements scale exponentially with the number of molecular orbitals for full configuration-interaction

Fig. 2. A schematic of pDMET, in which a mean-field description of the system (gray) is broken into N separate fragments (red) and the rest of the system is characterized by a quantum bath (blue) contracted to the same number of states as the fragment. The fragment-bath pairs can be solved for and propagated in parallel.

(FCI), the method currently implemented in RT-pDMET, the subsystems themselves are only a fraction of the size of the total system and can be solved in parallel, allowing for high accuracy with computational savings based on dimensionality reduction. [8]

II. GENERALIZED REAL-TIME DENSITY MATRIX EMBEDDING THEORY

Static pDMET proposes an approach for treating a large system, as shown as gray dots in Fig. 2, with a high level of accuracy by dividing a system into separate fragments. The nature of the fragments, represented by red dots in Fig. 2, is flexible, as they can be defined as sites on a lattice or as atoms or molecules. [9] The interaction of a single fragment with the rest of the environment is described in terms of a quantum bath the same size as the fragment itself, as shown by blue dots in Fig. 2. Once the fragment and bath states are defined, the electronic structure of the fragment-bath embedded pair, or ρ_{emb} in Fig. 2, can be solved using more accurate levels of theory, capturing the correlations between the fragment and its environment with the dimensionality reduction from the full mean-field description of the system. [9], [10] In the static formalism of pDMET, these separate fragment-bath solutions are averaged over to create a full “global” density matrix, ρ^{glob} , and this in turn is used to generate a new mean-field solution, ρ^{MF} . This process repeats until the mean-field description of the system converges, ensuring self-consistency within this methodology. [9], [10]

In the real-time extension of pDMET, the mean-field description of the system and each fragment-bath pair are both propagated in time, with the equations governing the time-dependence ensuring self-consistency. As a result, the self-consistency loop does not need to be repeated at every time-step in the simulation. [9] RT-pDMET is able to accurately characterize the dynamics of a system with a fragment as small as 5% of the total system size, as shown in Fig. 3. First applications show that RT-pDMET is able to capture dynamics even in regimes of strong electron correlation and high-levels of disorder while allowing for dramatic dimensionality reductions, making it a promising method to apply to larger systems. [9] Current work focuses on extending this methodology towards spin-generalized systems as well as

Fig. 3. Electron density of one site from a 60-site model as a function of time after Coulomb repulsion on the site is increased. The RT-pDMET results from a fragment composed of two sites (orange), four sites (blue), and five sites (pink) are compared against the exact result (black) and time-dependent Hartree Fock, an inexpensive, but less accurate methodology (green). [9] The RT-pDMET data is observed to converge to the exact result at a fraction of the cost of the exact calculation.

taking advantage of the fragment nature of the methodology by leveraging MPI for embarrassingly parallel propagation of each fragment-bath pair. This allows the workload of the code to be distributed over multiple nodes and shifts the rate-limiting step of the algorithm to that of the individual fragment-bath calculations.

III. CONCLUSION

Developing a better characterization of the CISS effect would contribute to a deeper understanding of the role spin plays in chiral systems, which has thus far been ignored in areas such as biochemistry. [4] The spin-generalized formalism of RT-pDMET will be a powerful tool in understanding the mechanism behind the CISS effect and will be used to study both model systems and atomistic systems. We anticipate its implementation to atomistic systems to be challenging due both to the increased computational expense. However, a successful real-time treatment of systems exhibiting the CISS effect would allow for important physical insight into the underlying mechanism.

RT-pDMET is not limited in application to only CISS. RT-pDMET would be able to model any system exhibiting strongly correlated electron dynamics and could be applied to other areas of charge and spin transport. [10] Because of its inherent parallelizability and flexibility in fragment size, RT-pDMET would be able to capture effects in systems larger than those that other real-time electronic structure methods would be able to describe. The development of RT-pDMET fills a current gap in the field of dynamic simulations based on quantum mechanics, offering accurate results via an inexpensive and flexible methodology.

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